

Antibiotic Susceptibility Pattern of *E. coli* and other Uropathogens Isolated from Patients Attending Martha Bamaiye General Hospital Zuru, Kebbi State Nigeria

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Submission: 21st January, 2024; Accepted 30th January, 2024; Published: 28th February, 2024

Abstract

This study was carried out to establish the prevalence of *E. coli* and others uropathogen and its drug susceptibility patterns among patients attending Martha Bamaye General Hospital, Zuru, Kebbi State, Nigeria. A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted on outpatients and inpatients presenting with symptoms of UTI. A purposeful sampling was used to obtain 385 respondents, and questionnaires were used to obtain demographic information from them. Mid-stream urine samples were obtained from the respondents using sterile bottles and bacterial isolates identification was done using biochemical tests. Risk factors associated with *E. coli* infection were collected using a questioner and analyzed at $\alpha=0.05$. Of the 385 urine samples, 112 (29 %) patients were confirmed positive for UTI. The prevalence of UTI was higher among females (62.1%), compared to males (37.9 %). *E. coli* are the most bacteria isolated among the uropathogens. Antimicrobial profiles of *E. coli* strains showed the following susceptibility patterns: nitrofuratoin (100 %), cefotaxime (86.3 %), ciprofloxacin (83.3 %), gentamicin (81.7 %), ampicillin (45.3 %), nalidixic acid (48.5 %), and cotrimoxazole (44.1 %). Furthermore, 85% of the isolates were observed to be multidrug resistant. The results showed that *E. coli* are the most causative agent of UTI and are sensitive to nitrofuratoin. Hence there is a need for constant monitoring of antibiotic resistance for better management of patients with UTI.

Keywords: Antimicrobials, Resistance, Susceptibility, Uropathogens

1.0 Introduction

Urinary tract infection (UTI) has been defined as the state in which bacteria actively multiply in the urine from urine formation in the kidney up to urethral meatus [13]. Peni *et al.* [11] reported that Urinary tract infection (UTI) is the colonization of the urinary tract by pathogenic microorganisms: namely bacteria, fungi, protozoa, yeast and viruses [21]. The infection in low economic setting causes high morbidity and mortality among population and high financial cost implications to the patients [22]. Bacteriuria is the commonest infection in sexually active non-pregnant women between the ages of 18-48years [2]. In healthy women the prevalence of bacteriuria increases with age. It happens more regularly in developing countries among the low-social financially viable population. This infection

is persistently associated with varying prevalent by age, sex, sexual activity and urinary tract abnormalities [3]. [6] Proposed that up to 95% of UTI develop by an ascending route from urethra and progresses upward to the bladder [4]. Symptomatic UTI can either be complicated or uncomplicated depending on patient anatomical or physical abnormality that triggers urinary tract infection [13]

E. coli strains usually produce haemolysin and aerobactin. They are resistant to the bactericidal action of urinary tract tissues causing acute pyelonephritis and acute cystitis. Patients with structural or functional deformities of the urinary tract are generally susceptible to infections caused by bacterial strains that possess haemolysin and aerobactin [18]. Other factors that may increase the risk for urinary tract infections include

infrequent voiding, incomplete voiding, personal hygiene, and sexual activity, use of spermicidal contraception, genetics, hormonal status and diabetes and immunosuppressant substances [10].

Multidrug resistance should be monitored worldwide and surveillance systems should be used to determine the aetiology for UTIs [11]. There is a worldwide setback in management of many bacterial infectious diseases due to antibiotic resistance [12]. It is estimated that globally 26 % of deaths are due to infectious diseases such as UTIs of which 98 % occur in low income countries [21].

There is pressure resulting from intensive and indiscriminate use of antibiotics in treatment leading to a rapid spread of antimicrobial agent resistance genes to uropathogens. In General hospital Zuru, there is lack of resources such as skilled manpower and laboratory facilities to efficiently carry out culture and sensitivity. This often leads to overuse of antibiotics thus causing antibiotic resistance. Therefore there was need to establish the prevalence and susceptibility pattern of uropathogens in this study area. Susceptibility testing of antibiotics is of great important to reduce reoccurrence of infections of UTIs and reduce treatment failure. Therefore it important to isolate and identify uropathogens, common microorganisms causing UTIs and evaluate their susceptibility patterns of the isolates causing UTIs among patients visiting this study area. To date, there are few or no studies carried out describing the uropathogens and their susceptibility pattern among patients in General Hospital Zuru Southern Kebbi. This study aimed at describing the major pathogens causing UTI among patients, the prevalence of UTI and establish susceptibility pattern of antimicrobial resistance in General hospital Zuru.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study population

The study target both male and female outpatients and inpatients presenting with symptoms and signs of UTI, which include dysuria, polyuria, fever, nausea, and flank pain were sampled for this study. Baseline demographic data including age, sex, level of education and risk factors such as catheterization, history of UTI, also out and in patients were also collected. Samples were collected during the period between May to December 2022.

2.1.1 Research criteria

The research criteria for the work include the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria include i) Adult patients and children whose parents/guardians provided consented ii) those patients presenting with clinical symptoms associated with UTI. Exclusion criteria include i) Patients who or whose relatives declined to sign consent forms. ii) The patients who were on antibiotic therapy within one week were excluded.

2.2 Collection of samples

Urine samples were collected from 385 patients using midstream technique for adults and urine bags for infants. In women, samples were taken after vulva swabbing with clear water. All specimens were analyzed as soon as possible after collection to avoid deterioration of leucocytes. Processing of the specimen was done to meet the required number set for that day [15].

2.3 Sampling design

Purposive sampling was used to select patients with UTI symptoms and then simple random sampling was used to select 10 patients per week until sample size of 385 was reached with 146 male and 239 female patients were used. This design was appropriate for the study since it provided baseline information concerning antibiotic susceptibility patterns of bacterial uropathogens in inpatients and outpatients attending Martha Bamaie General Hospital, Zuru [8].

2.4 Sample size determination

According to [5] prevalence of 50 % was considered since the prevalence of UTI of the patient was not available in this study area. The sample size was determined as follows:

$$N = \frac{Z^2 (PQ) D}{D^2}$$

Where: n=require sample; p= anticipated prevalence which was 50 % (0.5) in this study; q = failure which was calculated as 100-50 giving 50 % (0.5); Z= is the appropriate value from the standard normal deviate at 95 % level of confidence (1.96) in this study; d=degree of precision set at 5 %.

Sample size was $n = \frac{1.962(0.5 \times 0.5)}{0.05^2} = 385$

2.6 Bacterial identification of bacterial

The identification and characterization of bacteria isolates were done on the basis of cultural, colonial and morphological appearance on culture media and by conventional biochemical test [21].

2.6.1 Microscopy identification

The microscopy identification was done using the method described by Prakash and Saxen [21] was adopted, smear was made and allowed to dry in air, fixed by flaming, placed on rack and flooded with crystal violet (basic stain) and stained for 2-3 minutes. Slides were washed in running tap water until the stain stop running. Then the slide was covered with Lugol's iodine (mordant) for 30 seconds, and washed in tap water. Decolourization was made with a few drop of acetone in no time. The slide was washed thoroughly in water, and counterstained with diluted carbol fuchsin for half a minute, washed and blotted to dry with a filter paper. The prepared slides were examined under the microscope using oil-immersion lens. Bacteria colored red were labeled as Gram-negative organism while violet colored bacteria were labeled as Gram-positive.

2.6.2 Biochemical test used

The biochemical used were catalase, citrate, coagulase, indole, MRVP, motility and Oxidase test in accordance to the method described by Prakash and Saxen (21)

2.6.2.1 Catalase Test: A drop of 3% hydrogen peroxide solution was placed on a glass slide. A bit of growth was then removed from the solid medium with a wire loop and emulsified in the hydrogen peroxide. A positive test was indicated by prompt bubbling and frothing.

2.6.2.2 Citrate Test: This test uses Simmon's citrate agar to determine the ability of a bacteria to use citrate as its sole carbon source. Bacteria colonies are picked up by a straight wire and inoculated into slope of Simmons citrate agar and incubated overnight at 37 °C. If the organism has the ability to use citrate, the medium changes its color from green to blue.

2.6.2.3 Coagulase Test: A drop of physiological saline was placed on a clean glass slide and a colony picked from the solid medium was emulsified in the saline. A loopful of citrated human plasma was added to the bacterial suspension and mixed using the wire loop. The slide was then held up and tilted back and forth for one minute. A positive test is indicated by clumping of cells in the mixed suspension

2.6.2.4 Indole Test: Pure bacterial culture was grown in sterile peptone broth for 24 hours at 37°C. Following incubation, 5 drops of Kovac's reagent was added to the tubes. A positive indole test is indicated by the formation of a pink to red color in the reagent layer on top of the medium within seconds of adding the reagent.

2.6.2.5 Methyl Red-Voges Proskauer Test: This test uses MRVP broth. Bacteria isolates were grown in MRVP broth for 24 hours at 37°C After growth, the broth was separated into two different tubes, one for the Methyl Red (MR) test and one for the Voges-Proskauer (VP) test. The pH indicator Methyl Red was added to one tube and a red color indicated positive test. The VP test uses alpha-naphthol and potassium hydroxide to indicate a positive or negative test.

2.6.6. Oxidase Test: Two drops of 1% freshly prepared oxidase reagent (phenylenediamine) was placed on a filter paper in a clean Petri dish. The test organism was smeared on it with a glass rod. A positive result showed deep purple colour appearing within 5-30secs. The absence of deep purple colour indicates a negative result.

2.7 Antibiotic susceptibility testing

This test was performed using disc diffusion method as described by [7]. In this technique, organisms isolated were inoculated in normal saline with the help of sterile wire loop. Colonies were taken from culture plates after 24 hours into nutrient broth; and turbidity formed was adjusted to an equivalent of 0.5 McFarland. The test organism was streaked over the surface of Muller Hinton agar plates using sterile cotton swabs. Discs impregnated antibiotics, which were commercially available, were placed on plates firmly by means of sterile forceps aseptically and the inoculated plates were incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. Afterwards, diameters of zone of inhibition were measured in mm. The antibiotics used and their zones of sensitivity were measured using veneer calibre and graded according to

sensitive, intermediate or resistant [17]. The inoculated plates were air dried, and antibiotic discs were placed on Muller-Hinton agar using sterile forceps and gently pressed down to ensure contact. The following 8 antibiotic discs were used: Nitrofurantoin (NIT, 300µg), Cefotaxime (CEF, 10µg), Amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (AMC,

10µg), Gentamicin (GET, 10µg), Nalidixic acid (NA, 30µg) Ampicillin (AMP, 10µg), Ciprofloxacin (CIP, 25µg), and Cotrimoxazole (SXT, 25µg). Standard strains of *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and *S. aureus* were used as control during antimicrobial susceptibility testing [2].

Table 1: Standard antimicrobial inhibition zones according to Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute

Antibiotics	Resistant	Intermediate	Sensitive
Ampicillin (10µg)	≤13mm	14-16mm	≥16mm
Ciprofloxacin(30µg)	≤12mm	14-16mm	≥17mm
Co-trimoxazole (30µg)	≤10mm	11-15mm	≥16mm
Gentamicin(10µg)	≤12mm	13-14mm	≥15mm
Amoxicilin-lavulinic acid(10µg)	≤13mm	14-16mm	≥17mm
Nitrofurantoin(10µg)	≤14mm	15-16mm	≥17mm
Cefotaxime(10µg)	≤14mm	11-15mm	≥18mm
Nalidixic acid(30µg)	≤13mm	14-18mm	≥19mm

2.8 Data management and analysis

The antibacterial activity was reported in terms of diameter of the zones of inhibition (mm).

3.0 Results

Table 2: Prevalence of UTI at Martha Bamaye General Hospital, Zuru

	No of Examined	Positive	Negative	Prevalence (%)	Chi- square	P – value
Overall	385	112	273	29.09		
Gender						
Male	146	41	105	37.9	0.116	0.0412
Female	239	71	168	62.1		
Age Groups years						
1 – 14	32	8	24	8.3	2.918	0.012
15 – 24	124	39	85	32.2		
25 – 34	125	35	90	32.4		
35 – 44	68	22	46	17.7		
45 – 54	24	4	20	6.2		
55 and above	12	4	8	3.1		

Table 3: showed the biochemical test of the isolates

Bacteria	Biochemical Test								
	Catalase	Citrate	coagulase	indole	MR	VP	Motility	oxidise	Microscopy/ gram reaction
<i>E. coli</i>	+	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	-
<i>Klebseilla spp</i>	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
<i>Proteus spp</i>	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	-
<i>S. spp</i>	+	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	+

Key + = positive - = Negative

Table 4: Antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of *E. Coli* and other negative uropathogens bacteria isolated from urine culture for patients (n=82) at Martha Bamaye General Hospital Zuru

Bacterial isolates	No. of isolates (n)	Patterns	NIT n(%)	CET n(%)	AMC n(%)	GET n(%)	NAL n(%)	CIP n(%)	AMP n(%)	SXT n(%)
<i>E. coli</i>	66	S	53(80.3)	45(68.2)	20(30.3)	44(66.7)	19(28.8)	46(69.7)	22(33.3)	12(18.3)
		R	13(19.7)	12(18.1)	14(21.2)	10(15.1)	13(19.7)	9(13.6)	14(11.7)	17(25.8)
		I	0(0.0)	9(13.7)	32(48.5)	12(18.2)	34(51.5)	11(16.7)	30(45.5)	41(62.1)
<i>K. vulgaris</i>	12	S	7(58.3)	9(75.0)	8(66.7)	3(25.0)	6(50.0)	7(58.3)	0(0)	0(0.0)
		R	5(41.7)	3(25.0)	4(33.3)	3(25.0)	4(33.3)	2(16.7)	2(16.7)	2(16.7)
		I	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	6(50.0)	2(16.7)	3(25.0)	10(83.3)	10(83.3)
<i>Proteus ssp.</i>	6	S	4(66.7)	3(50.0)	3(50.0)	3(50.0)	3(50.0)	3(50.0)	2(33.3)	3(50.0)
		R	2(33.3)	2(33.3)	2(33.3)	2(33.3)	1(16.7)	1(16.7)	3(50.0)	2(33.3)
		I	0(0.0)	1(16.7)	1(16.7)	1(16.7)	2(33.3)	2(16.7)	1(16.7)	1(16.7)

AMP = ampicillin, CIP = ciprofloxacin, SXT = co-trimoxazole GET = gentamicin, AMC = amoxicilin + clavulinic acid, NIT= nitrofurantoin, CET= Cefotaxime, NAL= nalidixic acid. S=Sensitive, I=Intermediate, R=Resistant

Table 5: Antimicrobial susceptibility pattern Gram positive uropathogens isolated from urine culture for patients (n=36) at Martha Bamaye General Hospital Zuru

Bacterial isolates	No. of isolates (n)	Patterns	NIT N (%)	CET n(%)	AMC n(%)	GET n(%)	NAL n(%)	CIP n(%)	AMP n(%)	SXT n(%)
<i>S. aureus</i>	11	S	8(72.0)	9(81.0)	7(63.6)	3(27.0)	5(45.5)	3(27.3)	5(45.5)	3(27.3)
		R	3(27.0)	2(18.0)	4(36.4)	4(36.0)	2(18.2)	3(27.3)	3(27.3)	3(27.3)
		I	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	4(36.0)	4(36.4)	5(45.5)	3(27.3)	5(45.5)
CNS	25	S	17(69.0)	20(78.0)	17(69.6)	8(30.0)	3(13.0)	18(73.0)	5(21.7)	4(17.4)
		R	8(30.0)	5(22.0)	8(30.4)	5(21.0)	7(26.1)	7(27.0)	7(26.1)	8(30.4)
		I	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	12(47.0)	15(60.0)	0(0.0)	13(52.0)	13(52.2)

AMP = ampicillin, CIP = ciprofloxacin, SXT = co-trimoxazole GET = gentamicin, AMC = amoxicilin + clavulinic acid, NIT= nitrofurantoin, CET= Cefotaxime, NAL= nalidixic acid. S=Sensitive, I=Intermediate, R=Resistant

Table 6: Resistance pattern of bacterial isolates to more than two antibiotics of patients (N = 120) at Martha Bamaye general Hospital Zuru

Bacterial Isolate	Total (%)	R0	R1	R(> 2)
Gram Negative	84 (70.0)	5 (6)	0 (0)	79 (94)
<i>E. coli</i>	66 (80.5)	1 (1.2)	0 (0)	65 (98.5)
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae.</i>	12 (14.3)	3 (3.5)	0 (0)	8 (66.0)
<i>Proteu svulgaris</i>	6 (5.9)	1 (1.2)	0 (0)	5 (83.3)
Gram Positive	36 (30)	7 (19)	0 (0)	23 (63.8)
CNS	25 (69.4)	4 (16)	0 (0)	23 (92)
<i>S. aureus</i>	11 (30.5)	3 (27.3)	0 (0)	8 (72.7)
Total				120 (100)

R0- No antibiotic resistance, R1- Resistance to one, R2-Resistance to more than two drugs

Table 7: Risk factors associated with UTI at Martha Bamaye General Hospital, Zuru

N = 385		Frequency (%)	Positive	Negative	Chi- square	P – value
Education						
Illiterate	12	3.3	9	3	2.742	0.523
Primary	202	55.6	41	161		
Secondary	138	38.1	19	119		
Tertiary	11	3	2	9		
Catheterization						
Yes	57	14.8	17	40	0.17	0.0504
No	328	85.2	95	233		
History of UTI						
Yes	341	88.6	99	242	0.555	0.004
No	42	10.9	12	30		
Total		385				
Outpatient/ Inpatient						
Outpatient	355	92.2	83	272	72.024	0.000
Inpatient	30	7.8	29	1		
Symptoms						
Yes	338	98	98	236	0.895	0.017

4.0 Discussion

The results of this work reported a prevalence of 29.1 % (Table 2) at Martha Bamaie General hospital Zuru which is less than the prevalence of 36 % reported by [10]. The results showed that there was no significant difference between patient's level of education and UTI (P=0.523). This is because they were equally infected. This agrees with studies carried out by (14). The prevalence of UTI in patients with previous history of infection was significantly higher than of those without previous history (p=0.004). The results agreed with studies carried by Toronto et al [23]. This implies that there are resistance strains of bacteria from those who had previous history of urinary tract infection. The prevalence of UTI among the patients with previous history of catheterization was significantly higher than those without history of previous catheterization (P=0.0504). These finding agree with previous report by [16] and was associated with predisposing factors such long duration of catheterization and contamination of the urinary system during inserting of catheters [1].

The occurrence of Gram-negative bacteria was 68.3 % (82) while Gram-positive isolates 31.7 % (38) which was similar to rates 75 % and 25 %, respectively of isolation of Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria reported by [19]. Among the isolates, *E. coli* was the most predominant bacteria isolated (55 %). These high rates were due to the presence of the normal flora in the rectal and vaginal area. Anatomical and functional changes of females make it difficult to maintain

personal hygiene and as result increase the risk of acquiring UTI Susceptibility patterns of Gram-negative bacteria showed that all of the isolates were sensitive to nitrofurantoin (100 %). The rest of isolates were sensitive to ciprofloxacin (79.8 %), cefotaxime (75.3 %), amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (72.8 %) gentamicin (67.6 %), nalidixic acid (65.6 %) cotrimoxazole (46.6 %) and ampicillin (44%). It was in contrary, to a study reported at Tikur Ahbessa Specialized Hospital Addis Ababa, Ethiopia Assefa *et al.* (2008) which indicated that their susceptibility pattern of Gram-negative bacteria were Gentamicin (93.3 %), Chloramphenical (83.3%), Contrimoxazole (73.3 %) and amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (70 %) were highly resistant. Availability and indiscriminate use of commonly used antibiotics without health care workers prescription lead to an increased multidrug resistance. Due to the increasing multidrug resistance among uropathogens, the health care workers are left with a limited choice of routinely used antibiotics to choose from for the treatment of urinary tract infections (9). This can be attributed the fact that bacteria undergo mutation which makes their susceptibility vary from one geographical to the other (7).

Nitrofurantoin was found to be effective (100 %) to both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria this finding agrees with a previous report by [15]. It is used as a drug of choice for the treatment of uropathogens. Few of the isolated uropathogens showed resistance to more than two of the commonly used antibiotics. This was in agreement with findings of (25) and could be due to abuse, misuse and underuse of antibiotics (18).

Prevalence of multidrug resistance in this study was 85 % of the uropathogens isolated.

5 Conclusions

The findings of this research showed that *E. coli*, *Klebsiella spp.*, *Proteus spp.* and *Staphylococcus spp.* are the causative agents of UTI in the study area. In the 120 isolates were resistant for more than two antibiotics were recorded in 108 (90 %) isolates. Antibiotic susceptibility patterns of all patients with bacterial uropathogens will reduce multidrug resistance.

6 Recommendations

i) There is a need for continuous surveillance of antibiotic to the currently used antibiotics in management of urinary tract infections covering the entire Zuru Emirate.

ii) Continuous follow up to provide an update of laboratory diagnosis of urinary tract infections in order to reduce multidrug resistance bacteria in UTI patients.

iv) Health care workers should enforce health education to patients in order to adhere to the treatment and thereby reducing drug resistance.

v) Screening for resistance and identify modes of transmission.

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